

An efficient synthesis of *E*-2-amino-4-aryl-8-(arylmethylene)-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[*d*]pyrimidines and their lower analogues

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Abstract : Base-catalysed cyclocondensation of α,α' -bis(arylmethylene)cyclohexanones with guanidine hydrochloride has been found to generate *E*-2-amino-4-aryl-8-(arylmethylene)-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[*d*]pyrimidines in high yield, the structures of which have been established from their analytical and spectral data. The corresponding lower analogues, α,α' -bis(arylmethylene)cyclopentanones also were found to produce similar products viz. *E*-2-amino-4-aryl-7-(arylmethylene)cyclopenteno[1,2-*d*]pyrimidines in comparable yield under the same reaction condition.

Keywords : α,α' -Bis(arylmethylene)cycloalkanones, guanidine hydrochloride, *E*-2-amino-4-aryl-8-(arylmethylene)-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[*d*]pyrimidines, *E*-2-amino-4-aryl-7-(arylmethylene)cyclopenteno[1,2-*d*]pyrimidines.

Introduction

As a part of our continued interest in synthesis of new fused heterocycles having potential biological activities^{1,2}, recently we have carried out a synthesis of *E*-8-(arylmethylene)-4-aryl-1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8-octahydrobenzo[*d*]pyrimidine-2-thiones³ (**1**) by base-catalysed cyclocondensation of α,α' -bis(arylmethylene)cyclohexanones (**2**) with thiourea. We have also assigned the correct structure **3** to the monoacetyl derivative³ formed on treatment of these compounds with acetic anhydride, which showed acetylation site at the amino nitrogen.

Pyrimidine is a fundamental part of nucleic acids and has been associated with a number of biological activities⁴. Aminopyrimidines constitute one of the important classes of pyrimidines and their various derivatives have displayed interesting antibacterial⁵, antitumor⁶ and HIV-I inhibiting activities⁷. Also, the pyrimidine and aminopyrimidine structures are frequently occurring motifs in commercially available drugs such as anti-atherosclerotic aronixil, anti-anxiolytic buspirone, anti-psoriatic enazadrem and other medicinally relevant compounds. α,α' -Bis(arylmethylene)cycloalkanones (**2** and **4**), readily obtainable from cycloalkanones and aromatic aldehydes, were recently utilized by us for studying their reaction with indole⁹ and thiourea³. A survey of literature revealed

that their reaction with guanidine has not been studied so far, although the reports of cyclocondensation of varieties of α,β -unsaturated ketones with guanidine are long-known⁸. In this communication, we report a very efficient synthesis of some *E*-2-amino-4-aryl-8-(arylmethylene)-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[*d*]pyrimidines (**5**) and their lower analogues by base catalysed cyclocondensation of various α,α' -bis(arylmethylene)cycloalkanones with guanidine hydrochloride.

Results and discussion

This endeavour started by using α,α' -bis(phenylmethylene)cyclohexanone (**2a**) as the substrate. Thus, when a mixture of **2a** (1 mmol), guanidine hydrochloride (1.5 mmol), NaOH (4.5 mmol) and ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed on a water bath, a product started to be formed as indicated by TLC. After completion of the reaction within 4 h it was found that a single product was obtained in 65% yield. Analytical and spectral data of the product definitely showed that it was *E*-2-amino-4-phenyl-8-(phenylmethylene)-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[*d*]pyrimidine (**5a**). Mechanistically, **5a** was formed by 1 : 1 condensation of **2a** and guanidine followed by an aerial oxidation, a sequence of reactions already known in the cases of reaction of guanidine with various α,β -unsaturated ketones⁸.

Scheme 1

Propelled by these encouraging results, the reaction was then performed by using a variety of α,α' -bis(arylmethylene)cyclohexanones (**2**) and guanidine hydrochloride (Scheme 1). In all the cases, the reaction proceeded smoothly to give *E*-2-amino-4-aryl-8-(arylmethylene)-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[*d*]pyrimidine (**5**) and the results are summarized in Table 1.

Our attempts to synthesise the lower analogue of **5** by starting from α,α' -bis(arylmethylene)cyclopentanones (**4**) and use of the aforesaid reaction condition were successful and we got the products **6**.

Acetylation of one compound of the series **6** was studied and it gave only one monoacetyl derivative **7** having acetylation site at the amino nitrogen at 2-position.

Experimental

Melting points were recorded on a Kofler block and are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in KBr on a Perkin-Elmer 397 spectrophotometer. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded in CDCl₃ on Bruker AV-300 (300 MHz) spectrometers using TMS as internal standard. High resolution mass spectra were recorded on Micro Mass QTOF Spectrometer.

Table 1. Results of cyclocondensation of α,α' -bis(arylmethylene)-cycloalkanones with guanidine hydrochloride

Entry	Starting bis(arylmethylene)-cyclohexanone	Reaction time (h)	Isolated product	Yield (%)	M.p. (°C)
1	2a	4	5a	65	206–207
2	2b	4	5b	50	230
3	2c	2.5	5c	70	210–211
4	2d	3.5	5d	50	186–187
5	2e	4	5e	60	182–183
6	4a	3	6a	70	195–196
7	4b	3	6b	72	212–213
8	4c	2.5	6c	75	230
9	4d	3	6d	58	>300

[†]The products were characterised from their analytical and spectral data.

Analytical samples were routinely dried *in vacuo* at room temperature. Column chromatography was performed with silica gel (60–120 mesh) and TLC with silica gel G of SRL Pvt. Ltd. Petroleum ether had the boiling range 60–80 °C.

α,α' -Bis(arylmethylene)cyclohexanones and α,α' -bis(arylmethylene)cyclopentanones were easily prepared⁹ by condensation of available cycloalkanones and aromatic aldehydes in aqueous ethanolic sodium hydroxide and they were properly characterized^{3,9}.

General procedure for reaction of α,α' -bis(arylmethylene)cycloalkanones with guanidine hydrochloride :

A mixture of α,α' -bis(arylmethylene)cycloalkanones (1 mmol), guanidine hydrochloride (1.5 mmol), sodium hydroxide (5 mmol) and ethanol (20 ml) was refluxed for the required time (Table 1). The mixture was poured into ice cold water after completion of the reaction. The solid thus obtained was filtered off, washed with water until it was alkali free. The crude product was extracted with chloroform and dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate. The concentrate of the chloroform extract was chromatographed over silica gel using petroleum ether-ethyl acetate (4 : 1) as eluent to obtain the pure product.

Spectroscopic data of the synthesized compounds :

E-2-Amino-4-phenyl-8-(phenylmethylene)-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[d]pyrimidine (5a) : Light yellow crystalline solid; IR : ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3458, 3349 (NH₂), 2928 (ArC-H), 1634, 1563 (C=N) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz,

CDCl₃) : δ 1.76 (2H, br s, H₂-6), 2.74 (2H, br s, H₂-5), 2.93 (2H, br s, H₂-7), 6.97 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.33–7.64 (10H, m, Ar-H), 8.39 (1H, s, H-11); Anal. Calcd. for C₂₁H₁₉N₃ : C, 80.48; H, 6.11; N, 13.41; Found : C, 79.88; H, 6.21; N, 13.03.

E-2-Amino-4-methoxyphenyl-8-(4'-methoxyphenylmethylene)-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[d]pyrimidine (5b) : Light yellow crystalline solid; IR : ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3477, 3374 (NH₂), 2940 (ArC-H), 1623, 1541 (C=N) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.70–1.73 (2H, m, H₂-6), 2.68–2.72 (2H, m, H₂-5), 2.84–2.86 (2H, m, H₂-7) 3.84 (3H, s, *p*-OCH₃), 3.85 (3H, s, *p'*-OCH₃), 5.06 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.09 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 6.97 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.44 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.52 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 8.06 (1H, s, H-11); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 23.03 (C-6), 26.91 (C-5), 27.90 (C-7), 55.23 (OCH₃), 55.32 (OCH₃), 113.64 (two carbons), 113.69 (two carbons), 117.38, 129.70, 130.28 (two carbons), 130.53, 130.68, 131.48 (two carbons), 132.11, 159.07, 159.85, 160.39, 161.50, 165.87; HRMS (ESI) Calcd. for C₂₃H₂₃N₃O₂ (M+Na)⁺ : 396.95; found 396.96. Anal. Calcd. for C₂₃H₂₃N₃O₂ : C, 73.97; H, 6.21; N, 11.25; Found : C, 73.76; H, 6.36; N, 10.93.

E-2-Amino-4-chlorophenyl-8-(4'-chlorophenylmethylene)-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[d]pyrimidine (5c) : Light yellow crystalline solid; IR : ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3448, 3357 (NH₂), 2928 (ArC-H), 1636, 1594 (C=N) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.71–1.75 (2H, m, H₂-6), 2.63–2.68 (2H, m, H₂-5), 2.81–2.85 (2H, m, H₂-7), 5.25 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.24 (2H, d, *J* 9.1 Hz), 7.39 (2H, d, *J* 10.2 Hz), 7.44 (2H, d, *J* 9.1 Hz), 7.50 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 8.01 (1H, s, H-11); ¹³C NMR (CDCl₃, 75 MHz) : δ 22.87 (C-6), 26.62 (C-5), 27.69 (C-7), 118.30, 127.47 (C-11), 12.42 (two carbons), 128.48 (two carbons), 130.03 (two carbons), 131.06 (two carbons), 131.27, 132.40, 135.01, 136.19, 136.89, 159.83, 161.04, 161.74.

E-2-Amino-4-methylphenyl-8-(4'-methylphenylmethylene)-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[d]pyrimidine (5d) : Light yellow crystalline solid; IR : ν_{\max} (KBr) : 3281, 3151 (NH₂), 2927 (ArC-H), 1625, 1541 (C=N) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃) : δ 1.71–1.72 (2H, m, H₂-6), 2.38 (3H, s, *p*-CH₃), 2.40 (3H, s, *p'*-CH₃), 2.66–2.68 (2H, m, H₂-5), 2.86–2.88 (2H, m, H₂-7), 5.19 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.20 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.37 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.44 (2H, d, *J* 7.8

H_z), 7.53 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 8.10 (1H, s, H-11); Anal. Calcd. for C₂₃H₂₃N₃: C, 80.90; H, 6.79; N, 12.31; Found: C, 80.61; H, 6.86; N, 12.01.

E-2-Amino-4-(2-furyl)-8-(2'-furylmethylene)-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[*d*]pyrimidine (**5e**): Light yellow crystalline solid; IR: ν_{\max} (KBr): 3385, 3219 (NH₂), 2927 (ArC-H), 1645, 1560 (C=N) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 1.85–1.89 (2H, m, H₂-6), 2.91–3.00 (4H, m, H₂-5 and H₂-7), 5.03 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.48 (1H, br s), 6.55 (2H, br s), 7.04 (1H, d, *J* 2.4 Hz), 7.50 (1H, br s), 7.62 (1H, br s), 7.87 (1H, br s); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 22.13 (C-6), 26.01 (C-5), 27.31 (C-7), 111.75, 111.88, 113.28, 114.64, 116.72, 117.52, 132.71, 143.14, 144.31, 151.57, 152.17, 154.55, 161.54, 162.07; Anal. Calcd. for C₁₇H₁₅N₃O₂: C, 69.61; H, 5.15; N, 14.33; Found: C, 69.32; H, 5.02; N, 14.16.

E-2-Amino-4-phenyl-7-(phenylmethylene)cyclopenteno[1,2-*d*]pyrimidine (**6a**): Light yellow crystalline solid; IR: ν_{\max} (KBr): 3326, 3184 (NH₂), 2926 (ArC-H), 1620, 1551 (C=N) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 3.17 (4H, br s, H₂-5 and H₂-6), 5.25 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.24–7.90 (11H, m, Ar-H and H-10); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 28.04 (C-5), 29.12 (C-6), 123.35, 125.76, 127.73, 128.30 (two carbons), 128.52 (two carbons), 128.56 (two carbons), 129.53 (two carbons), 129.82, 136.95, 137.83, 140.04, 162.13, 162.90, 170.58; Anal. Calcd. for C₂₀H₁₇N₃: C, 80.24; H, 5.72; N, 14.04; Found: C, 80.16; H, 5.96; N, 13.67.

E-2-Amino-4-chlorophenyl-7-(4'-chlorophenylmethylene)cyclopenteno[1,2-*d*]pyrimidine (**6b**): White crystalline solid; IR: ν_{\max} (KBr): 3314, 3175 (NH₂), 2935 (ArC-H), 1626, 1558 (C=N) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 3.14–3.17 (4H, m, H₂-5 and H₂-6), 5.24 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.38 (2H, br s), 7.47 (4H, br s), 7.54 (1H, br s), 7.86 (2H, d, *J* 6.3 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 28.05 (C-5), 28.97 (C-6), 123.13, 124.79, 128.75 (two carbons), 128.77 (two carbons), 129.64 (two carbons), 130.61 (two carbons), 133.58, 135.24, 135.99, 136.13, 140.15, 160.82, 162.65, 170.47.

E-2-Amino-4-methylphenyl-7-(4'-methylphenylmethylene)-cyclopenteno[1,2-*d*]pyrimidine (**6c**): Light yellow crystalline solid; IR: ν_{\max} (KBr): 3310, 3185 (NH₂), 2917 (ArC-H), 1623, 1540 (C=N) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 2.38 (3H, s, *p*-CH₃), 2.42 (3H, s, *p*'-

CH₃), 3.14–3.19 (4H, m, H₂-5 and H₂-6), 5.08 (2H, s, NH₂), 7.21 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.28 (2H, d, *J* 7.8 Hz), 7.46 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz), 7.53 (1H, s, H-10), 7.80 (2H, d, *J* 8.1 Hz); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 21.37 (*p*-CH₃), 21.45 (*p*'-CH₃), 28.23 (C-5), 29.19 (C-6), 123.16, 125.30 (C-10), 128.30 (two carbons), 129.24 (two carbons), 129.35 (two carbons), 129.52 (two carbons), 134.33, 135.35, 137.72, 139.31, 139.64, 162.21, 163.13, 170.60.

E-2-Amino-4-(2-furyl)-7-(2'-furylmethylene)cyclopenteno[1,2-*d*]pyrimidine (**6d**): Light yellow crystalline solid; IR: ν_{\max} (KBr): 3317, 3182 (NH₂), 2927 (ArC-H), 1624, 1547 (C=N) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 3.20–3.24 (4H, m, H₂-5 and H₂-6), 5.27 (2H, s, NH₂), 6.49–6.51 (1H, m), 6.53–6.54 (1H, m), 6.59–6.61 (1H, m), 7.21 (1H, br s), 7.39 (1H, br s), 7.53 (1H, br s), 7.66 (1H, br s).

Acetylation of 6a: The compound **6a** (0.2 mmol) was heated with acetic anhydride (2 ml) in presence of pyridine (2 drops) on a boiling water bath for 2 h. The reaction mixture was cooled and worked up in the usual way. Column chromatography of the crude product so obtained over silica gel furnished the compound **7**, white crystalline solid (CHCl₃-pet ether). Yield 85%; m.p. 216–217 °C; IR: ν_{\max} (KBr): 3183 (N-H), 1662 (NHCOCH₃), 2925 (ArC-H), 1610, 1560 (C=N) cm⁻¹; ¹H NMR (300 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 2.68 (3H, s, COCH₃), 3.25–3.34 (4H, m, H₂-5 and H₂-6), 7.31–7.68 (8H, m, Ar-H), 7.68 (1H, s, H-10), 7.96 (2H, d, *J* 3.6 Hz), 8.36 (1H, br s, N-H); ¹³C NMR (75 MHz, CDCl₃): δ 25.41 (CH₃), 28.57 (C-5), 28.98 (C-6), 126.89, 127.33, 128.17, 128.49 (two carbons), 128.67 (two carbons), 128.70 (two carbons), 129.67 (two carbons), 130.45, 136.50, 137.23, 139.04, 156.90, 161.21, 171.14, 178.01 (C=O); Anal. Calcd. for C₂₂H₁₉N₃O: C, 77.40; H, 5.61; N, 12.31; Found: C, 76.91; H, 5.86; N, 12.04.

Conclusion:

Two novel series of fused aminopyrimidines, viz. *E*-2-amino-4-aryl-8-(arylmethylene)-5,6,7,8-tetrahydrobenzo[*d*]pyrimidines and *E*-2-amino-4-aryl-7-(arylmethylene)cyclopenteno[1,2-*d*]pyrimidines could be synthesized very easily in moderate to good yield. The synthesized compounds might be able to work as important intermediates and potential new drugs. Further work for biologi-

cal activities such as antibacterial, antimalarial, antihypertensive activity etc. are being undertaken and the results will be presented in future.

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References

1. (a) F. Chattopadhyay and A. K. Mallik, unpublished work; (b) A. K. Mallik, S. P. Dey, F. Chattopadhyay and A. Patra, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 2002, **43**, 1295; (c) A. K. Dey, S. K. De, A. K. Mallik and T. Ganguly, *Spectrochimica Acta, Part A*, 2001, **57**, 1427; (d) S. K. De and A. K. Mallik, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A & B*, 1997, **36**, 537; (e) M. G. Dhara, U. K. Mallik and A. K. Mallik, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1996, **35**, 1214.
2. A. K. Mallik, F. Chattopadhyay, D. K. Dey, A. Patra and A. Elmali, *J. Chem. Res.*, 2004, 180.
3. R. Pal, T. K. Mandal and A. K. Mallik, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2009, **86**, 402.
4. K. L. Sayle, J. Bentley, F. T. Boyle, A. H. Calvert, Y. Cheng, N. J. Curtin, J. A. Endicott, B. T. Golding, I. R. Hardcastle and P. Jewsbury, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2003, **13**, 3079.
5. S. Chandrasekaran and S. Nagarjan, *Il Farnaco*, 2005, **60**, 179.
6. M. T. Cocco, C. Congiu, V. Lilliu and V. Onnis, *Bioorg. Med. Chem.*, 2006, **14**, 366.
7. V. R. Gadhachanda, B. Wu, Z. Wang, K. L. Kuhen, J. Caldwell, H. Zondler, H. Walter, M. Havenhand and Y. He, *Bioorg. Med. Chem. Lett.*, 2007, **17**, 260.
8. (a) V. A. Chebanov, S. M. Desenko and T. W. Gurley, "Azaheterocycles Based on α,β -Unsaturated Carbonyl", Springer-Verley, Berlin, 2008, p. 61; (b) M. B. Deshmukh, K. N. Alasundkar, S. M. Salunkhe, D. K. Salunkhe, S. A. Sankpal, D. R. Patil and P. V. Anbhule, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2008, **47**, 1915.
9. A. K. Mallik, R. Pal and T. K. Mandal, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 2007, **46**, 2056.

